

STUDY OF COMPLEX IONS IN SOLUTION BY THE METHOD OF THERMOMETRIC TITRATION

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The older graphical method of representing the thermometric data has been modified by introducing a correction for the heat change due to dilution during the course of titration. Some anomalous results recorded in the literature have also been explained with the help of this modification.

In the previous communications (Chatterji, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 366; *1958, 35, 57; Chatterji and Ghosh, *ibid.*, 1957, 34, 407) the author has shown that a correction factor due to dilution must be introduced to get the actual heat changes taking place in thermometric titrations involving precipitation and acid-base neutralisation reactions. The plot of the computed values of the visual thermal changes against the volume of the titrant gives curves showing more accurate end-points than those obtained by the older method of plotting. In the present paper the same method of plotting has been recommended in the study of complex-ion formation in solution by thermometric titration. Certain anomalous results recorded in the literature can be easily explained by this means. Two such cases have been discussed here to illustrate the situation and the advantages of using the modification proposed by the author.

Halder (*ibid.*, 1946, 23, 205) measured the heat changes arising from mixing solutions of CdSO_4 and KI in different concentrations and obtained breaks in the heat change—composition curves, indicating reactions between Cd^{2+} and I^- ions when these were present in the molar ratios 1:1, 1:3, 1:4 and 1:5 respectively. In fact, the occurrence of reactions in the ratios 1:1, 1:3 and 1:5 is difficult to explain and is not supported by other methods of study.

Purakayastha (*ibid.*, 1947, 24, 257) employing the same method has indicated the stepwise formation of the complex ions $[\text{BeF}_3]^{1-}$, $[\text{BeF}_4]^{2-}$, $[\text{BeF}_5]^{3-}$ and $[\text{BeF}_6]^{4-}$ in the interaction between BeF_2 and NH_4F . Here also the existence of the last three ions lacks further evidence.

In both of the above mentioned cases, no allowance was, however, made for the dilution of the solution taken in the Dewar flask during titration, and the observed temperature changes were directly plotted against the volume of the titrant to get the thermometric curves. It is highly probable that the dilution factor alone can account for some of the breaks in the titration curves of the foregoing workers. In that case, doubtful breaks should disappear if the corrected temperature changes, ΔT_{Cv} are plotted against the volume of the titre added. As before

$$\Delta T_{Cv} = \frac{\Delta T (V + dv)}{V},$$

where ΔT = the observed temperature changes in $^{\circ}\text{C}$, V = original volume in c.c. of the solution taken in the Dewar vessel, and dv = volume of the titre added in c.c.

* In the January issue of 1958, in the paper by Chatterji, the following corrections are to be made. In Table IV (p. 60), figures under columns 2 and 3 refer to % and not to g., as printed.

The plots of ΔT and ΔT_{CV} respectively against the volume of the titre in the cases discussed above, are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

According to Halder (*loc.cit.*), the break at $\text{Cd}^{2+} : \text{I}^- = 1 : 1$ is due to the reaction

The second break at $\text{Cd}^{2+} : \text{I}^- = 1 : 3$ has been explained as due to the simultaneous formation of $\text{Cd}(\text{CdI}_4)$ and K_2CdI_4 in solution.

No other evidence has been provided by Halder as to the formation of $\text{K}_2\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ in solution.

So far as the second break is concerned, a more plausible explanation would have been to ascribe it to the formation of the ion $[\text{CdI}_3]^-$, but Halder failed to get any indication of its formation by the thermometric titration of CdI_2 with KI .

In the corrected temperature curve (Fig. 1) the breaks at $\text{Cd}^{2+} : \text{I}^- = 1 : 1$, and $1 : 3$ are no longer shown, but the break at $\text{Cd}^{2+} : \text{I}^- = 1 : 4$ is clearly shown, which indicates that the ion $[\text{CdI}_4]^{2-}$ exists as a stable species in solution.

FIG. 1

The last break at 1 : 5, which occurs in both the curves, possibly does not indicate any true reacting proportion of Cd^{2+} and I^- . The heat changes after the formation of $[\text{CdI}_4]^{2-}$ is also very small. The downward trend of the curve is obviously due to the fall in the temperature of the mixture in absence of any reaction, the titre added being at a lower temperature than that of the system in the Dewar.

The effect of volume correction on the thermometric curve of Purakayastha (*loc.cit.*) is even more exemplary (Fig. 2). Only one reaction is indicated, the reacting proportion of $\text{Be}^{2+} : \text{F}^-$ being 1 : 4. Thus, the only ion which is stabilised in solution is $[\text{BeF}_4]^{2-}$

The other complexes suggested by Purakayastha thus have their origin in the wrong method of representation of the thermometric data.

FIG. 2

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